

Eligibility

Record ID

Participant's initials

(ABC or A-B)

INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Aged $\geq$ 18 years Yes
 No

2. Patient willing and able to give written informed consent Yes
 No

3. Diagnosed with pleural effusion on CT or US Yes
 No

4. Patient attending for therapeutic aspiration Yes
 No

5. Known or suspected malignancy as the underlying cause of the effusion Yes
 No

6. In the Investigator's opinion, is able and willing to comply with all study requirements Yes
 No

Please make sure that all the Inclusion Criteria= YES

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Patients who are pregnant or lactating Yes
 No

2. Pleural infection or other condition requiring admission and chest drain insertion Yes
 No

3. Known transudative pleural effusion or pleural effusion clinically thought to be primarily due to cardiac, renal or hepatic impairment Yes
 No

Please make sure that all Exclusion Criteria = NO

Eligibility criteria confirmed

Eligible to take part in study
 Ineligible to take part in study

Name of researcher completing eligibility

Date of completing eligibility

Baseline

Record ID

BASELINE ASSESSMENT

Date of Visit

Hospital Site

- University Hospitals Plymouth NHS Trust
- Oxford University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust
- Norfolk and Norwich University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust
- University Hospitals of Leicester NHS Trust
- North Bristol NHS Trust

Participant's initials

(ABC or A-B)

Demographics

1. Age

2. Sex

- Male Female

3. Mode of presentation

- Emergency (required drainage 0-1 days from presentation)
- Urgent (required drainage 2-7 days from presentation)
- Routine

4. Is patient currently inpatient/outpatient?

- Inpatient Outpatient
 None

4.1. If yes to inpatient, Admission Date:

Symptoms

5. Duration of symptoms?

(Days)

(Weeks)

(Months)

What symptoms has the patient experienced?

6. Breathlessness Yes No7. Chest pain Yes No8. Cough Yes No9. Fevers Yes No10. Night sweats Yes No

Effusion

11. When was the effusion first diagnosed?

12. Side of effusion aspiration Right Left

13. Has the patient had previous ipsilateral drainage procedures?

 Therapeutic aspiration
 Chest Drain
 IPC
 Thoracoscopy
 VATS
 None

13.1 Date of therapeutic aspiration

13.2 Date of chest drain

13.3 Date of IPC

13.4 Date of thoracoscopy

13.5 Date of VATS

Past Medical History

14. Is the effusion known to be Malignant? No Yes Suspected

14.1. Tumour type

- Breast
 Lung
 Mesothelioma
 Lymphoma
 Ovarian
 Renal
 Colorectal
 Other

14.1a. If Other, please specify tumour type

14.2. Date of Diagnosis

(If exact date unknown, enter as '01-M-Y' or '01-Jan-Y')

14.3. Previous chemotherapy

- Yes
 No

14.4. Previous radiotherapy

- Yes
 No

14.5. Previous surgery

- Yes
 No

14.6. Current chemotherapy

- Yes
 No

14.7. Current radiotherapy

- Yes
 No

15. Performance status (ECOG 0-4)

- 0
 1
 2
 3
 4

16. Chronic renal failure (eGFR < 60)

- Yes
 No

17. Cardiac failure

- Yes
 No

18. Liver failure

- Yes
 No

19. Current use of diuretics

- Yes
 No

Observations

20. Oxygen saturations on air

(0-100%)

21. Respiratory rate (breaths/minute)

(0-50 breaths/min)

Therapeutic Aspiration

22. Volume of fluid drained during therapeutic aspiration

(0-3000mL)

23. Reason for stopping aspiration

- Target drainage volume reached
- Fluid stopped draining
- Patient became symptomatic
- Complications
- Other

Chest radiograph

24. Chest radiograph uploads

Pre procedure Post procedure

24.1. CXR pre-procedure

24.1a. Pre-procedure CXR Date

24.1b. Pre-procedure CXR uploaded image

24.2. CXR post-procedure

24.2a. Post-procedure CXR Date

24.2b. Post-procedure CXR uploaded image

Ultrasound

25. Ultrasound

Pre procedure Post procedure

25.1 Ultrasound pre-procedure

25.1a. Pre-procedure Depth of effusion

(cm)

25.1b. Pre-procedure Height of effusion

(cm)

25.1c. Pre-procedure Septated

- No
- Mild
- Moderate
- Heavy

25.2 Ultrasound post-procedure

25.2a. Post-procedure Depth of effusion

(cm)

25.2b. Post-procedure Height of effusion

(cm)

25.2c. Post-procedure Septated

- No
 Mild
 Moderate
 Heavy

Sample Storage

26. Blood sample collected for long term storage

- Yes
 No

27. Pleural fluid samples collected for long term storage

- Yes
 No

Name of researcher completing the form

Date of completing the form

Eq5d5l

Record ID

Please click the ONE box that best describes your health TODAY.

MOBILITY

- I have no problems in walking about
 - I have slight problems in walking about
 - I have moderate problems in walking about
 - I have severe problems in walking about
 - I am unable to walk about
-

Please click the ONE box that best describes your health TODAY.

SELF-CARE

- I have no problems washing or dressing myself
 - I have slight problems washing or dressing myself
 - I have moderate problems washing or dressing myself
 - I have severe problems washing or dressing myself
 - I am unable to wash or dress myself
-

Please click the ONE box that best describes your health TODAY.

USUAL ACTIVITIES (e.g. work, study, housework, family or leisure activities)

- I have no problems doing my usual activities
 - I have slight problems doing my usual activities
 - I have moderate problems doing my usual activities
 - I have severe problems doing my usual activities
 - I am unable to do my usual activities
-

Please click the ONE box that best describes your health TODAY.

PAIN / DISCOMFORT

- I have no pain or discomfort
 - I have slight pain or discomfort
 - I have moderate pain or discomfort
 - I have severe pain or discomfort
 - I have extreme pain or discomfort
-

Please click the ONE box that best describes your health TODAY.

ANXIETY / DEPRESSION

- I am not anxious or depressed
- I am slightly anxious or depressed
- I am moderately anxious or depressed
- I am severely anxious or depressed
- I am extremely anxious or depressed

We would like to know how good or bad your health is TODAY.

(0-100)

This scale is numbered from 0 to 100.

100 means the best health you can imagine.

0 means the worst health you can imagine.

Please enter a number that indicates how your health is TODAY.

VAS_Diary

Record ID

Baseline Breathlessness VAS score

(0-100mm)

Not done

Day1 Breathlessness VAS score

(0-100mm)

Not done

Day2 Breathlessness VAS score

(0-100mm)

Not done

Day3 Breathlessness VAS score

(0-100mm)

Not done

Day4 Breathlessness VAS score

(0-100mm)

Not done

Day5 Breathlessness VAS score

((0-100mm))

Not done

Day6 Breathlessness VAS score

(0-100mm)

Not done

Day7 Breathlessness VAS score

(0-100mm)

Not done

Blood Results

Record ID

Participant's initials

(ABC or A-B)

Date bloods taken

Haemoglobin

(g/L)

Total White cells

($\times 10^9/L$)

Neutrophils

($\times 10^9/L$)

Lymphocytes

($\times 10^9/L$)

Platelets

($\times 10^9/L$)

CRP

(mg/L)

Total protein

(g/L)

eGFR

(mL/min/1.73m²)

LDH

(U/L)

NT-proBNP

(ng/L)

CXR

12. CXR upload Yes
 No

12a. Day 7 CXR Date _____

12b. Day 7 CXR uploaded image

13. Depth of effusion _____
(cm)

14. Height of the effusion _____
(cm)

15. Septated No
 Mild
 Moderate
 Heavy

Name of researcher completing the form _____

Date of completing the form _____

Day 7 Review

Record ID

Date of Visit

Participant's initials

(ABC or A-B)

1. Has participant died?

Yes No

1.1. Date of death

1a. Cause of death 1a

1b. Cause of death 1b

2. Cause of death 2

2. Has the patient had any further pleural fluid drainage procedures since the enrolment therapeutic aspiration?

- Therapeutic aspiration
- Chest Drain
- IPC
- Thoracoscopy
- VATS
- None

2.1.a. Date of Therapeutic aspiration

2.2.a. Date of chest drain

2.3.a. Date of IPC

2.4.a. Date of Thoracoscopy

2.5.a. Date of VATS

3. Has patient had any planned pleural procedures cancelled due to a lack of fluid?

Yes No

3.1. Date

3.2. Type

Therapeutic aspiration Chest drain IPC Thoracoscopy VATS

Pleural Fluid Results

4. Total protein

(g/L)

5. Glucose

(mmol/L)

6. pH

7. LDH

(U/L)

8. Cytology

Malignant cells Atypical cells
 Negative

9. Culture

Positive
 Negative

Inpatient

10. If the patient was enrolled as an inpatient, have they been discharged?

No Yes N/A

10.1. Date of discharge?

Emergency

11. Has patient been admitted as an emergency due to breathlessness caused by pleural fluid since enrolment?

Yes
 No

11.1. Date of admission

Day30 Review

Record ID

Date of Visit

1. Has participant died?

Yes No

Participant's initials

(ABC or A-B)

1.1. Date of death

1a. Cause of death 1a

1b. Cause of death 1b

2. Cause of death 2

Pleural

2. Has the patient had any further pleural fluid drainage procedures since day 7?

- Therapeutic aspiration
- Chest Drain
- IPC
- Thoracoscopy
- VATS
- None

2.1a. Date of Therapeutic aspiration

2.2a. Date of chest drain

2.3a. Date of IPC

2.4a. Date of Thoracoscopy

2.5a. Date of VATS

3. Has patient had any planned pleural procedures cancelled due to a lack of fluid?

Yes
 No

3 Month Review

Record ID

Date of Visit

Participant's initials

(ABC or A-B)

1. Has participant died?

Yes No

1.1. Date of death

1a. Cause of death 1a

1b. Cause of death 1b

2. Cause of death 2

Pleural

2. Has the patient had any further pleural fluid drainage procedures since day 30?

- Therapeutic aspiration
- Chest Drain
- IPC
- Thoracoscopy
- VATS
- None

2.1a. Date of Therapeutic aspiration

2.2a. Date of chest drain

2.3a. Date of IPC

2.4a. Date of Thoracoscopy

2.5a. Date of VATS

3. Has patient had any planned pleural procedures cancelled due to a lack of fluid?

Yes
 No

3.1. Date

3.2. Type

Therapeutic aspiration Chest drain IPC Thoracoscopy VATS

Inpatient

4. If the patient was an inpatient at last follow up, have they been discharged?

No Yes N/A

4.1. Date of discharge?

Emergency

5. Has patient been admitted as an emergency due to breathlessness caused by pleural fluid since day30? Yes
 No

5.1. Date of admission

5.2. Still inpatient?

Yes
 No

5.3. Date of discharge

New Treatment

6. Has the patient started any new treatments for the underlying cause of their effusion? Yes
 No

6.1. If Yes, Which treatment?

- Chemotherapy
 Radiotherapy
 Surgery
 Immunotherapy
 Hormonal Therapy
 Diuretics
 Other

Name of researcher completing the form

Date of completing the form

Withdrawal

Record ID

Participant Initials

1. Date of withdrawal

2. Indicate reason for early withdrawal

- Withdrawal of participant consent
- Ineligibility to take part in the study
- Significant protocol deviation
- Loss to follow up
- Other

3. Comment for reason

Name of researcher completing the form

Date of completing the form
